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DEVELOPMENT OF UV SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF LETROZOLE IN PURE AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

Siddharth M. Patil*, Sunil T. Galatage, Avinash U. Choudhary

Department of Pharmaceutics, KLE'S College of Pharmacy, Nippani, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

In this present research work we developed a validated UV spectrometric method for Letrozole. It is simple, fast, accurate, cost efficient and reproducible spectrophotometric method, developed for the estimation of Letrozole in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form. Based on measurement of absorption of UV light, the spectra of Letrozole in acetonitrile as a solvent showed maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) at 240 nm. The calibration curve was plotted over the concentration range from 1-24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Letrozole with correlation coefficient 0.999. Validation was performed as per ICH Q2 guidelines for linearity, accuracy, precision, and recovery. This method has good reproducibility with % RSD less than one. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification were found to be 0.0470 and 0.1424 respectively by simple UV spectroscopy. Thus proposed method can successfully applied for Letrozole in routine analysis work.

Corresponding author

Mr. Sidharth M. Patil

Asst. Professor in the dept. of pharmaceutics,
K. L. E. Society's College of Pharmacy, Nippani.
+919448941936.
priyaharsha@rediffmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Chemically Letrozole is 4,4'-(1,2,4-triazol-1-ylmethyl)dibenzonitrile.¹

Letrozole is white to yellowish crystalline powder, practically odorless.²

It is freely soluble in dichloromethane, slightly soluble in ethanol, and practically insoluble in water.³

It used in the treatment of breast cancer in women who have gone through "the change of life" (menopause). Anastrozole works by lowering estrogen hormone levels to help shrink tumors and slow their growth.⁴

It has molecular formula $C_{17}H_{11}N_5$, having mol.wt.285.31.^{5,6}

Letrozole is a reversible (Type II), nonsteroidal aromatase inhibitor. Aromatase catalyzes the final and rate-limiting step in the conversion of androgens to estrogens in peripheral tissues. This occurs mainly in adipose tissue, but also in normal and malignant breast tissues, and provides the main source of estrogen in postmenopausal women.

The goal of hormone therapy in breast cancer is to deprive tumour cells of estrogens, which are implicated in the development of tumours.^{7,8} Maximal estrogen suppression is produced by a 0.1 mg dose,^{7,9} although a higher dose (ie, 2.5 mg per day) was associated with increased clinical responses.⁷

Maximal estrogen suppression occurs 48-78 hours after a single dose.¹⁰

Highly selective blockade of aromatase does not interfere with the production of other steroids (eg, adrenal corticosteroids, aldosterone)^{11,12} or thyroid stimulating hormone.⁹

Letrozole does not have progestogenic, androgenic or estrogenic activity.^{11,12} Differences in the mechanism of action may contribute to the apparent lack of cross-resistance between steroidal (eg, exemestane) and nonsteroidal (eg, anastrozole, letrozole) aromatase inhibitors.¹³

Till the present day there is no valid UV spectrophotometric method available for estimation of Letrozole using acetonitrile as a solvent. The goal of our present research work was to develop a validated UV spectrometric method for determination of Letrozole in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form and uses these results for analysis of drugs in pharmaceuticals as it is rapid, economic, and effective for quality control of pharmaceutical formulations containing Letrozole by UV spectroscopy.

Figure no. 1- Structure of Letrozole.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instrumentation, Reagents and Chemicals:

Instrument:

Instrument used were:

UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer Shimadzu UV1800 with one cm matched quartz cells. Electronic Balance, Model-AJ-Vibra, Mfg.by Essae-Teraoka Ltd. Japan.

The glass wares used in each procedure were soaked overnight in a mixture of chromic acid and sulphuric acid rinsed thoroughly with double distilled water and dried in hot air oven prior to use. The absorption spectra of reference and test solution were carried out in a one cm quartz cell over the range of 200-400 nm.

Material:

Pure samples:

Letrozole was kindly gifted by Zydus- Cadila Pharamaceuticals, Goa, India.

Reagents and Chemicals:

Acetonitrile-Methyl cyanide (Loba Chemie.Private Limited, Mumbai, India), other reagents & chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of standard stock solution:**I Stock solution**

Standard drug solution of Letrozole was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure Letrozole in small amount of acetonitrile in 100 ml volumetric flask and then the volume was adjusted with acetonitrile the resultant solution gives the concentration of 1 mg/ml ie.1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

II stock solution

From I stock solution 10 ml solution was taken and then diluted up 100 ml with same solvent in a volumetric flask and then the concentration of this stock was 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Determination of Lambda Max. (λ_{max}):

10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ solution was prepared by withdrawing 10ml of solution from II stock solution and further diluted with acetonitrile to get concentration. This solution was then scanned at wavelength of 200 to 400 nm against blank. The λ_{max} was found to be at 240 wavelengths where absorbance was maximum at this wavelength. Hence this is considered as absorption maxima which are used for preparation of calibration curve. (Figure no. 2).

Figure no. 2: Determination of λ_{max} of letrozole.

Preparation of Calibration Curve:**I Stock solution**

Standard drug solution of Letrozole was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure Letrozole in small amount of acetonitrile in 100 ml volumetric flask and then the volume was adjusted with acetonitrile the resultant solution gives the concentration of 1mg/ml ie.1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

II stock solution

From I stock solution 10 ml solution was taken and then diluted up 100 ml with same solvent in a volumetric flask and then the concentration of this stock was 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

From this II stock solution 01, 02,06,06,08,10,12,14,16,18,20,22 and 24 ml solutions were pipetted and volume was made to 100 ml using acetonitrile as a solvent to get concentrations of 01, 02,04,06,08,10,12,14,16,18,20,22 and 24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The absorbance of these solutions was measured at 240 nm (λ_{max} of Letrozole). The standard calibration curve was obtained for data of concentration v/s absorbance; standard calibration curve data reported in (Table no.1, Figure no.3).

Table 1: Calibration data for the method development for Letrozole.

Sr.No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 240nm \pm standard deviation
1	1	0.160 \pm 0.002
2	2	0.276 \pm .0026
3	4	0.574 \pm 0.0025
4	6	0.856 \pm 0.0036
5	8	1.134 \pm 0.0029
6	10	1.461 \pm 0.00264
7	12	1.722 \pm 0.00304
8	14	1.982 \pm 0.00359
9	16	2.266 \pm 0.0024
10	18	2.610 \pm 0.00307
11	20	2.915 \pm 0.0021
12	22	3.217 \pm 0.00234
13	24	3.567 \pm 0.00381

Figure. 3: Calibration Curve for letrozole.

METHOD VALIDATION:**Linearity and Range:**

The linearity of response was obtained between 01 to 24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentrations. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting the absorbance versus the concentration data and was treated by linear regression analysis (Table no. 3). The equation of the calibration curve for Letrozole obtained was $y = 0.146x - 0.024$, and calibration curve was found to be Linear in the above mentioned concentrations. The correlation coefficient (R^2) was 0.999 shown in the Figure no.3.

Precision:**Repeatability:**

Precision of the method was analysed by repeatability and determined by analyzing 06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Letrozole for six times the results are reported in (Table no. 2).

Table no. 2: Data showing Repeatability of Absorbance's.

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Wavelength (nm)	Absorbance	Mean \pm S.D.	%R.S.D
1		240	0.853		
2		240	0.858		
3		240	0.854		
4	6	240	0.854	0.856 \pm 0.00275	0.321
5		240	0.857		
6		240	0.860		

S.D. = Standard Deviation, R.S.D.= Relative Standard Deviation.

Precision:

Precision of the method was studied as intra-day and inter day variations. Intraday precision was determined by analyzing 04, 08, 12, µg/ml of Letrozole for three times within the day. Inter-day precision was determined by analyzing same concentration of solutions daily for three days; the results are reported in (Table no. 4).

Table no. 4: Results for Intra-day and Inter-day precision of Letrozole.

Drug	Conc. (µg/ml)	Intra-day Mean Abs.	Absorbance ± S.D.	%RSD	Inter-day Mean Abs	Absorbance ± S.D.	%RSD
Letrozole	4	0.574	±0.00254	0.435	0.562	±0.00253	0.450
	8	1.142	±0.00360	0.315	1.237	±0.00264	0.213
	12	1.734	±0.002080	0.119	1.714	±0.0045	0.262
Mean %RSD				0.2896			0.3083

Standard Deviation and Relative Standard Deviation (S.D and R.S.D).

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification (LOD and LOQ)

Determination of the detection and quantification limits was performed based on the standard deviations of y-intercept and the slope of the least square line parameters as defined in the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) Q2 guidelines. The LOD and LOQ were 0.0470µg/ml and 0.1424 µg/ml respectively and data is reported in (Table no.3).

Table no 3: Validation parameters for Fosfestrol.

Sr. No.	Parameters	Results
1	Absorption maxima (nm)	240 nm
2	Linearity range (µg/ml)	1-24µg/ml
3	Standard Regression Equation	y = 0.146x - 0.024
4	Correlation coefficient (R ²)	R ² = 0.999
5	Specificity	A 6 µg /ml solution of Letrozole in solvent acetonitrile at UV detection of 240 nm will show an absorbance value of 0.856±0.00275
6	Accuracy (% Recovery)	99.80
7	Precision RSD Repeatability (n=6)	0.321
	Intra-day(n=3)	0.2896
	Inter-day(n=3)	0.3083
8	Molar Absorptivity	4.1419*10 ⁴ L/mol.cm.
9	LOD	0.0470µg/ml
10	LOQ	0.1424 µg/ml

n=no. of determinations, LOD=Limit of Detection, LOQ =Limit of Quantification, RSD= Relative Standard Deviation.

Recovery Study:

To analyse the accuracy of developed method, it was applied to analyse commercially available Letrozole tablet (FEMPRO 2.5 mg.-CIPLA). Fifty tablets were weighed and powdered. The amount of tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of Letrozole was weighed accurately and transfer to 100 ml volumetric flask then 10 ml of acetonitrile as a solvent was added and kept for 15-20 min with frequent shaking and volume was made up to mark with given solvent. The solution was then filtered through Whatman filter paper. This filtrate was diluted suitably with solvent to get the solution of 05 µg/ml concentration. The absorbance was measured against blank solution. The recovery experiment was performed at three different levels that are 80%, 100%, 120%. To the preanalyzed sample solution, a known amount of standard drug solution was added at three different levels and absorbance was recorded. The drug content of the preparation was calculated using standard calibration curve. Amount of drug estimated by this method is given in (Table no. 5).

Table no. 5: Determination of Accuracy by Percentage Recovery Method.

Drug	Tablet amount (µg/ml)	Level of addition (%)	Amount added (µg/ml)	Amount recovered (µg/ml)	%Recovery	Average % Recovery
Letrozole	05	80	8	12.979	99.83	99.80
	05	100	10	14.972	99.81	
	05	120	12	16.958	99.75	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Attempt has been made to develop rapid, sensitive, economic, precise and accurate analytical method for Letrozole in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form. The proposed method based on UV spectrometric absorption in UV region using acetonitrile as a solvent, maximum absorbance was found to be at 240 nm LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.0470 and 0.1424 respectively. The proposed method showed molar absorptivity 4.1419×10^4 L/mol.cm. The calibration curve of Letrozole plotted at 240 nm (Figure no. 3) and linear relationship was obtained between 0.1-24 µg/ml. The accuracy of the method was determined by calculating mean percentage recovery it was found to be, 99.80% (Table no.5). Further precision was calculated as repeatability, inter and intraday variations and % RSD was less than one given in (Table no. 4).

CONCLUSION:

An UV spectrophotometric method for Letrozole in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form has been developed and validated. The method is precise, selective, accurate and linear over concentration range studied. The proposed method is applicable for quality control, routine analysis and determination of Letrozole in pure and pharmaceutical dosage form.

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